

The Effect of Training and Development on Workers Performance in Coffee Factory at Coorg District

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Abstract: workers are the major assets of any business. Human resource management play an important role in every organisation and it include manpower planning, orientation, performance appraisal, recruitment, selection, motivation etc. among these training play an important key function in the organization. Every business needs well trained workers to perform the activities effectively. Training and development leads to better performance of workers and the success of the organization depends on workers performance. Training is the best method to create personal to the organization and also trained employees are the biggest strength and it creates job satisfaction, commitment morality, innovative mind and reduce labour turnover. in this dynamic era training is the most precious competent and challenging for business. It is enhancing the quality of work life of the workers and development the organization. The aim of the study is the effect of training and development on workers performance. The study found that employees are motivated through training; training and development results into higher performance. the study reveals that there is need for consistent training and development taking into higher productivity of organization as well as workers.

Keywords: Training, Development, Workers, Performance;

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1. INTRODUCTION

We are living in a dynamic world. the world is becoming small market and our business is becoming larger in the world. In this result organization must be competitive to face the challenges in this dynamic environment. In this context training is the best method to create personal in the organization. trained employees are the biggest strength and it creates better job performance and great commitments to the business because they lead to high productivity in the same field. This leads to making them compete in global level and also the top-level management should provide a continuous training program for all workers in order to improve the performance and making them global masters. in this process the organization should started adopting effective and innovative training methods likes on the job training, off the job training, online training, audio visual training etc. the method of training varies from industry-to-industry institute to institute and private to public.

Present organizations are facing huge competition, changing technological and business environment. Globalization and test of customer needs have added more challenges on business

organization. In this regard to meet these challenges the industry needs to well-trained employees to the organization. Workers are the most precious asset for any institution as they can destroying or build goodwill of a company and they can affect economically. Training is more present day oriented add focus on specific skills ability to immediately performs and enhance their behaviour attitudes and performance of the employees in an organization. It is the process of increasing the ability and skill of an employee for doing a particular job effectively and efficiently. Training ease of much importance in achieving the goal of the organization by keeping interest of employees and organization. Development easy long term teaching process utilising by which managerial personnel learn conceptual and theoretical knowledge for general purpose. Training and development reveal that enhancing the ability of the employees for achieving the organizational objectives. Training is seen as useful means of technological innovation market competition organizational structuring and enhance workers performance. the objective of the study is to prove the effect of training and development on workers performance in the business.

Training and development have become one of the needed functions in every organization, because they need to high performance in the same field and are important part of human resource department, it has a significant effect on the success of an organization through improving workers performance

The dynamic organizations should deal with training importance linked up with alternating and growing international of industry diverse national point of view under varied workforce. training is much most important in achieving the objectives of the organization by keeping in view the sake of the employees and organization. Forms are now facing new challenges due to the rapid pace of technological and global development first of technological advancement have brought about the need of competencies and capabilities needed to perform a specific task. In order to face these challenges more enhanced and efficient training process are needed by all business.

2. Literature review

Training and development will improve employee skill knowledge and abilities and also create job satisfaction and even training program can help the organization to cut down the cost in the recruitment process (Karim 2019). There is a strong relationship between training and development practices and employee performance and training certainly increased the performance level and also shining a corporate image and organization should provide training for all cadre and in order to maintain homogeneous enhancement (Sanyal 2018).

There has been many research conducted on this subject. There is a higher degree of training will be higher productivity in automobile and agriculture industry. training place a major role in employee productivity revenue is interlinked process in the organization (Singh 2010). Training brings positive satisfaction to the employees and states that best instructors give overall satisfaction towards employee's performance and satisfaction with complete training. The successful training depends on the employees and as well as management (kalaiselvi 2012). The organization should follow the systematic training cycle regularly it helps to restructure of employees training methods and suggested that before training and after training should be in a systematic manner and follow ups are mandatory (rajathi 2014)

2.1 Employee training

Training is a learning that it is indispensable part of human resource in an organisation. training is an important element to an employee for the development of the companies because some of lack of knowledge skills and competencies a fail to accomplish task on timely basis. Besides training is the learning activity directed towards the adopting on the specific knowledge and skill for the purpose of an occupation or task.

According to Jyoti Sheeba (2020), trained employees are the biggest assets to the organization for staff so employers should be considered training is an investment not cost. Training and development should be designed and developed effectively and need to analyse the employee performance by the organization and training will not make employees perfect until it put into

action. Effective training programs helps to the organization and individuals like motivation to learn promoting learning culture and developing 2 non routine cognitive job done by people effectively and innovatively

However, Pattanaik (2017), employees' education and cadre are highly influenced their perception of training effectiveness in both sector like private and public, because qualified and highly profile employees acquired the training benefits easily and effectively also education is the major influence on adopting the training in effectively. And also training and development should be designed and developed effectively and need to analyse the employee performance by the organization. training will not make employee perfect until it put into action and it helps to organization and individuals like motivation to learn promoting learning culture and developing people effectively and innovatively. (Taiwo 2019), in traditionally lower-level employees were trained and higher-level employees were developed but in dynamic environment training and development must need it too all level employees and the management should conduct seminar workshop and systematic approach and has to find out the gap in the department who needed the training and evaluation of performance after training is mandatory

Motadu(2012), manufacturing industries make more effort in training programs compared to technology industries. Training contributes towards growth and development of both organization and individuals. it helps to create innovative mind and motivate the employees. anitha (2017), there is a strong positive relationship between staff commitments through the training and training should be systematic and standardised with advanced technology like audio visual aids. Nehru (2016), the demographical factor is very much influence on training practices and also preciously the employees age between 26-30 are best utilise of training. The training program impact on employees with positive relationship with the levels of job satisfaction and the attrition level will be low and also majority of employees stated that on the job method has been more effective.

2.2 Worker's development

Workers are always regarded with the development in future enhancing skill which leads to workers motivation and reduce turnover. there is no doubt that a well-trained and developed workers will be a valuable asset to the organisation and thereby will increase the chances of their efficiency and effectiveness in discharging their duties. On the other hand, development means those learning opportunities design to help workers to growth development is not primarily knowledge oriented instead it provides the skills and attitudes which will be useful to employers in higher level. development programs are regarded as specific framework for helping workers to develop their individual and professionals' skills ability attitudes knowledge and consequently improve their abilities to perform specific work in the business. It provides knowledge about business environment management principles and techniques human relations specific industry analysis and the like is needfull for better management of company. workers development focused on turning out human resource that is needed for effective performance in the organization (drucker 1999).

According to Adeniyi (1995) manpower development methods includes under study job rotation self-development and self-assessment. Despite (ashwathappa 2000) also suggested that if the training and development function is to be effective in the future and yields all expected returns, it will useful to move beyond its concern with techniques and traditional roles. On the other hand, development focus on building the knowledge and skills of organizational members so that they will be prepared to take on new competitiveness. basically, employee development includes training education and career development for staff it also includes exchange of knowledge and experience.

3. Objectives of the study

The study finds that the impact of training and development on workers performance. This research works shows at it training and development as on HRM practices and its effect on employee performance in the organization. Definitely the aim of the study is to find out

- The effect of training and development on workers performance
- The effect of training on employee satisfaction
- The need of employee training in organization
- The impact of training and development program has built morality towards organization

4. Methodology of the study

4.1. Sample and data collection

6 questionnaires were distributed among the different workers in the organization. 6 question is where completed information required the response rate was agreeable. Convenience sampling techniques was used for the research. The data was gathered by using self-administered questionnaire.

4.2. Measures and skills

In this study 2 variables were used training and development and workers performance. 6 questions of training and development and employee performance were used first of all variables were measured using gay 5 points like scales in which fi represented strongly agree to which is strongly disagreeing

4.3. Analysis and results

The main purpose of this study is to evaluate the impact of training and development on worker performance in the business. Here data have been gathered on the sampled respondents on the impact of training and development on worker performance, job satisfaction of the organization. total number of 30 employees were selected to provide answer to the structured questionnaires. Analysis of survey data is given below.

Figure 1: Do you think training and development has positive impact on performance?

In this chat saying that 70% workers are strongly agreed that they can improve their performance through the training where 15% workers are agreed this training content and 5% people are neutral and 10% workers are not agreed about the training programmes.

Figure 2: Does the training lead you to be satisfied with your organization?

From this chart it is clear that 58% of workers are strongly agreed that they can be satisfied in training after getting 24% are agreed with training content and 4% workers are not satisfied in training programs.

Figure 3: Does training and development is compulsory for the employees to do better work?

From the above table 69% of workers agreed that training is very much needed for better work life and 11% of workers are agreed and 10% of workers are neutral and 8% of workers are disagreed about training content.

Figure 4: Do you think training and development program has built morality towards organization?

From the above table 50% of workers are strongly agreed that training helps to build morality towards organisation. on the other hand 18% of workers are agreed about training content and also 24% workers are disagreed about training.

Figure 5: Does training program helps to reduce labour turnover?

From the analysis 51% of workers are strongly agreed that training helps to employees to retain in the organisation and also 15% of workers disagreed about training content.

Figure 6: Do you think the training improves your ability, skills, knowledge, strength and attitude?

From the above table saying that 51% of workers are strongly believed that training helps to improve their skills and knowledge and attitude and 15% workers are strongly disagreed in this content.

Discussion and finding of the study

Training is one of the most important tools which can lead to many possible benefits for both workers and business that helps to reach goal of the organization. This study reveals the impact of training and development on workers performance. the objective is to evaluate and analyse the effect of training and development of workers performance. To achieve these objectives a sample of 30 respondents were selected. The study revealed some findings like average employees strongly believe that training improve skill knowledge and abilities and it helps to create their job satisfaction of employees this statement is similar with the view of doctor Kareem (2019). Basically, better performance depends on proper training to workers.

Recommendation

Many organizations have come to know the important role of the training and development program as it enhances the organization staff efficiency, skills and productivity. In order to achieve the benefit of training initiative. The research shows that there is a strong impact of training and development on workers performance. All workers of the organization find their training and development beneficial for their performance. Employer should be provided to all levels of employees of training programs in order to reduce industrial accidents and labour turnover. On the other hand, its mandatory to employer should follow up after training.

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